

Engineering Property of Salt-Contaminated Clay: Mechanistic Insights from Diffuse Double Layer Evolution and Salt Crystallization Effect with Liquid Limit Prediction

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Full Paper Submitted to
Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering

Fig. S1 Sampling site of the natural clay

Fig. S2 Particle diameter distribution of the natural clay: **(a)** full-range grading curve; **(b)** fine fraction distributions

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Table S1 Mineralogical and clay mineralogical compositions of the natural clay

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Table S1 Mineralogical and clay mineralogical compositions of the natural clay

Category	Mineral	Content (%)
Primary Minerals	Quartz	43.0
	Plagioclase	9.0
	K-Feldspar	2.4
	Amphibole	1.4
	Magnetite	N.D.
	Calcite	18.0
	Dolomite	1.2
	Total (primary minerals)	75.0
Clay minerals	Illite/Smectite mixed-layer	32.2
	Illite	39.0
	Kaolinite	20.0
	Chlorite	8.8
	Total (clay minerals)	25.0

Note: The content of individual clay minerals is the percentage relative to the total clay fraction (25.0%)

Table S2 Characteristic particle diameter and grading parameters of the salt-contaminated clay samples

Salt type	Concentration (mmol/100 g)	d_{10} (μm)	d_{30} (μm)	d_{50} (μm)	d_{60} (μm)	d_{90} (μm)	Cu	Cc	Grading
Control group	0	1.068	6.16	23.13	27.69	47.86	25.93	1.28	Well-graded
	5	1.033	5.45	19	23.51	46.87	22.76	1.22	Well-graded
Na ₂ SO ₄ group	10	0.9	4.71	16.42	20.66	44.6	22.96	1.19	Well-graded
	40	1.603	8.15	25.12	30.93	61.85	19.3	1.34	Well-graded
	80	1.445	7.44	23.45	28.23	49.9	19.54	1.36	Well-graded
	5	1.049	8.87	17.56	21.05	41.31	20.07	3.56	Poorly-graded
NaHCO ₃ group	10	1.055	8.44	17.13	21.36	47.89	20.25	3.16	Poorly-graded
	40	1.051	8.35	16.87	20.51	44.94	19.51	3.23	Poorly-graded
	80	0.712	5.37	12.04	16.53	44.2	23.22	2.45	Well-graded
NaCl group	5	1.007	10.36	18.49	23.63	48.18	23.47	4.51	Poorly-graded
	10	1.37	14.38	23.79	29.03	53.39	21.19	5.21	Poorly-graded
	40	1.544	15.15	25.09	30.43	56.93	19.71	4.89	Poorly-graded
	80	1.948	17.31	29.47	36.07	69.89	18.52	4.26	Poorly-graded

Table S3 Literature sources used for liquid limit data compilation

No.	Salt-contaminated soil type	Salt content (%)	concentration (mmol/100 g)	Liquid limit ω_L (%)	Data source
1		0.330	2.323	21.20	Liang (2024)
2		0.337	2.373	30.00	Yang (2022)
3		0.373	2.626	41.79	Lu et al. (2025)
4		0.381	2.682	28.00	Niu (2021)
5		0.590	4.155	27.80	Zeng et al. (2025)
6		0.697	4.907	22.97	Luo (2023)
7		0.860	6.055	32.30	Yang et al. (2025)
8	Na ₂ SO ₄ - salt contaminated soil	1.300	9.152	29.41	Zhang et al. (2025)
9		2.490	17.530	28.10	Han et al. (2023)
10		3.100	21.825	28.81	Han et al. (2025)
11		3.700	26.049	26.30	Chi (2024)
12		4.601	32.392	31.80	Kang et al. (2025)
13		5.000	35.201	30.30	Ju et al. (2025)
14		6.670	46.959	27.90	Duan et al. (2024)
15		8.290	58.364	27.95	Yang (2022)
16		0.250	2.976	31.52	Wang et al. (2021)
17		0.330	3.928	34.90	Chen (2022)
18		0.370	4.404	46.70	Li (2024)
19		0.404	4.809	36.40	Shu et al. (2024)
20		0.420	5.000	37.50	Wang et al. (2020)
21		0.450	5.356	31.20	Shen et al. (2024)
22		0.510	6.071	36.66	Cheng et al. (2022)
23		0.550	6.547	35.10	Bao et al. (2018)
24	NaHCO ₃ - salt-contaminated soil	0.560	6.666	26.57	Nan et al. (2024)
25		0.634	7.547	33.00	Han (2023)
26		0.710	8.451	45.75	Shan et al. (2025)
27		0.710	8.451	50.87	Chen et al. (2023)
28		0.712	8.475	32.00	Han et al. (2023)
29		1.050	12.499	34.34	Xu et al. (2025)
30		1.100	13.094	32.00	Xu et al. (2024)
31		1.269	15.105	35.25	Liu (2023)
32		1.420	16.903	43.00	Cheng et al. (2021)
33		1.420	16.903	51.00	Shen et al. (2022)
34		1.700	20.236	33.40	Yao (2024)

35		0.830	14.203	29.73	Pei et al. (2024)
36		0.879	15.041	28.90	Xu et al. (2025)
37		1.080	18.481	33.10	Deng et al. (2025)
38		1.410	24.127	21.51	Dong et al. (2018)
39		1.870	31.999	27.11	Zhang (2024)
40		1.960	33.539	34.40	Zhou et al. (2006)
41	NaCl- salt contaminated soil	2.300	39.357	47.98	Hao (2023)
42		2.650	45.346	29.70	Wei (2021)
43		3.000	51.335	30.60	Li et al. (2021)
44		5.000	85.558	37.35	Ding (2019)
45		5.410	92.574	29.73	Pei et al. (2024)
46		5.977	102.276	33.56	Wang et al. (2024)
47		8.651	148.033	33.50	Maimaitiyusupu et al. (2019)
48		9.100	155.716	25.90	Wang (2024)
